

Synthesis and spectral studies of mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II) with carbonyl compounds

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Abstract : Complexes of the type $[\text{CoLL}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (where HL = salicylaldehyde, HL' = 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone; HL = 2-hydroxyacetophenone, HL' = 2-hydroxypropiophenone; HL = pentane-2,4-dione, HL' = 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione, 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione; HL = 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione, HL' = 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione) have been synthesized by the reactions of cobalt(II) nitrate with two different carbonyl compounds in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios. These have been characterized by elemental analyses, conductances, magnetic moments, thermal analyses and IR, electronic and FAB mass spectra.

Keywords : Mixed ligand complexes, cobalt(II), spectral study, thermal analysis.

The mixed ligand complexes have wide applications in microelectronic industry, chemical vapour deposition of metals, metal ion catalysed reactions¹⁻⁴, in the study of toxic effects of metal ions, detoxification mechanisms and drug designing⁵. They appear in biological fluids, create specific structures and manifest themselves as enzyme metal ion-substrate complexes⁶. Hence, the studies on mixed ligand complexes may help in understanding the role of metal ions in the active sites of metalloenzymes. Thambidurai *et al.*⁷ have reported Co^{II} mixed ligand complexes $[\text{Co}(\text{BTA})(\text{X-acac})]_2$ (where BTA = benzotriazole, X = Cl or Br, Hacac = acetylacetonate). Patel *et al.*⁸ have studied the characteristics and antimicrobial activities of Co^{II} mixed ligand complexes of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{sal})_2(\text{acphen})]$ or $[\text{Co}(\text{Brsal})_2(\text{acphen})]$ (where sal = salicylaldehyde, Brsal = 5-bromosalicylaldehyde and acphen = bis(acetophenone)-ethylenediamine) against bacterial strands using the agar diffusion method. However, the mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} with hydroxyaryl aldehydes and ketones or β -diketones have not been reported so far. Earlier mixed ligand complexes of Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and alkaline earth metals of the type MLL' {where M = Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} } and $[\text{MLL}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ {where M = Mg^{II} , Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} , Ba^{II} or Ni^{II} } with aldehydes and ketones have been reported from these laboratories⁹⁻¹¹. In the present paper, synthesis and characterization of mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} of the type $[\text{CoLL}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (where HL = salicylaldehyde (salH), HL' = 2-hydroxyacetophenone (hapH), 2-hydroxypropiophenone (hppH); HL = 2-hydroxyacetophenone, HL' = 2-hydroxypropiophenone; HL = pentane-2,4-dione (acetylacetonate, acacH), HL' = 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione (benzoylacetone, bzacH), 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione (dibenzoylmethane, dbzmH);

HL = 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione, HL' = 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione) are described.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of mixed ligand complexes.

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II}

Compd./Colour	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analyses (%) :			μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Cond. ($\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)
			Found (Calcd.)				
			C	II	Co		
[Co(sal)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂] Yellow	140	79	50.01 (51.29)	4.41 (4.58)	16.03 (16.77)	3.96	10
[Co(sal)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂] Yellow	260	47	51.96 (52.61)	4.87 (4.96)	15.96 (16.13)	3.90	11
[Co(hap)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂] Brown	200	48	53.22 (53.84)	5.02 (5.31)	15.71 (15.54)	3.90	15
[Co(acac)(bzac)(H ₂ O) ₂] Pink	160	40	50.21 (50.71)	5.49 (5.67)	16.39 (16.59)	4.01	30
[Co(acac)(dbzm)(H ₂ O) ₂] Yellow	142	35	56.98 (57.56)	5.18 (5.31)	14.03 (14.21)	4.75	30
[Co(bzac)(dbzm)(H ₂ O) ₂] Yellow	180	88	61.89 (62.64)	4.90 (5.05)	12.08 (12.29)	4.51	32

Results and discussion

The reactions of the hydrated metal ions with hydroxyaryl aldehydes and ketones and β -diketones in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios result in the formation of mixed ligand complexes (Scheme 1). The cobalt(II) complexes are yellow solids. They are insoluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, nitrobenzene and methanol but soluble in DMF. The characteristics and analyses of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. The conductances of the complexes are very low ($10\text{--}32 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) indicating their non-electrolytic nature¹². A large number of mixed ligand complexes in which cobalt(II) is hexa-coordinated have been reported^{13–15}.

In TLC, all the mixed ligand complexes show single spots with R_f values being intermediate of the two corresponding symmetrical bis-complexes indicating that these are mixed ligand complexes rather than a mixture of the two corresponding bis-complexes.

Thermogravimetric analysis of one representative complex [Co(hap)(hpp)(H₂O)₂] has been carried out and the presence of two coordinated water molecules is confirmed by the weight loss of 9.9% (calcd. for two water molecules 9.49%) at $\sim 140^\circ\text{C}$. Thereafter, a continuous loss in weight is observed and finally the complex is converted to cobalt oxide (wt. left 22.2%, calcd. for CoO 19.7%).

In the electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes bands at ~ 11200 , $16000\text{--}18000$ and $19000\text{--}24000 \text{cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) transitions respectively¹⁶. Sankhla *et al.*¹⁷ have observed bands at 18800cm^{-1} (ν_2) and $\sim 21000 \text{cm}^{-1}$ (ν_3) due to such transitions in the electronic spectra of the mixed ligand complexes of the type $\text{CoL}_2\text{L}'$ (where L = acetylacetonate, methylacetoacetate or ethylacetoacetate and

L' = ethylenediamine, propylenediamine or 8-hydroxyquinoline). A strong band at $\sim 30000 \text{cm}^{-1}$ is due to charge transfer¹⁸.

In the IR spectra of the mixed ligand complexes strong absorption bands in the region $1600\text{--}1650 \text{cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to coordinated $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$. In free salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone, acetylacetonate and benzoylacetone absorption bands due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ have been reported at 1660 , 1650 , 1640 , 1724 and 1724cm^{-1} respectively¹⁹. Thus the lowering of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ in mixed ligand complexes as compared to free ligands supports the coordination of C=O groups to the metal atom. Such shifts of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ to lower wave number side (1605cm^{-1}) have been reported by Panda and Mohapatra²⁰ in case of Co^{II} chelates of the type CoL_2Q_2 (where HL = *o*-hydroxyacetophenone, Q = quinoline). Weak to medium intensity bands observed in the complexes in the region $400\text{--}500 \text{cm}^{-1}$, which are absent in the free ligands, may be attributed to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ vibrations²¹. A broad band appears at $3300\text{--}3422 \text{cm}^{-1}$ which may be attributed to $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ of water associated with the complexes^{16,22}.

The μ_{eff} values (3.90–4.75 B.M.) at $\sim 300 \text{K}$ for Co^{II} complexes are in the range expected for a d^7 system. Slightly higher values may be due to the orbital contribution to the magnetic moment. The μ_{eff} values in the range 4.7–5.0 B.M. have been reported for bis-complexes of Co^{II} with salicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde²³. Das and Dash²⁴ have reported μ_{eff} values in the range 4.7–5.1 B.M. for mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} of the type $[\text{CoLL}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (where HL = benzoylacetone, HL' = 1,2- or 4-mono-substituted imidazole, 1,2-disubstituted imidazole, 4-methylmorpholine or 4-ethylmorpholine).

Table 2. Mass spectral data of mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} (*m/z* values and relative abundances)^a

Ions	[Co(sal)(hap)]	[Co(sal)(hpp)]	[Co(hap)(hpp)]
M ⁺	315 (2.7%)	329 (10.8%)	343 (5.5%)
CoL ⁺	180 (12.2%)	180 (16.2%)	194 (13.5%)
CoL ⁺	—	—	208 (10.8%)
CoL ₂ ⁺	301 (2.7%)	—	329 (8.1%)
CoL ₂ ' ⁺	329 (5.4%)	—	357 (8.1%)
[Co ₂ L ₂ L' ₂] ⁺	630 (2.7%)	—	686 (2.7%)
[Co ₂ LL' ₂] ⁺	509 (2.7%)	537 (2.7%)	551 (100%)
[Co ₂ L ₂ L' ₂] ⁺	436 (8.1%)	509 (2.7%)	537 (86%)
Co ₂ L ₃ ⁺	481 (100%)	481 (100%)	523 (29.7%)
Co ₂ L ₃ ' ⁺	523 (1.3%)	565 (1.2%)	565 (29.7%)
Co ₂ L ₄ ⁺	602 (40.5%)	602 (37.8%)	658 (16.2%)
Co ₂ L ₄ ' ⁺	—	—	714 (5.5%)
Co ₂ L ₅ ⁺	723 (54.1%)	723 (35.1%)	793 (10.8%)
Co ₃ L ₅ ⁺	782 (40.5%)	782 (18.9%)	852 (32.4%)

^aAll the fragments have been denoted as positive ions irrespective of whether they are odd electron or even electron species.

FAB mass spectra of three mixed ligand complexes [Co(sal)(hap)] (1), [Co(sal)(hpp)] (2) and [Co(hap)(hpp)] (3) have been recorded and the spectrum of [Co(hap)(hpp)] is reproduced in Fig. 1. The *m/z* values of the peaks along with their intensities relative to the base peak are given in Table 2. All the complexes exhibit molecular ion (M⁺) peaks, though not very intense, Co(sal)(hap)⁺ (*m/z* 315, 2.7%), Co(sal)(hpp)⁺ (*m/z* 329, 10.8%) and Co(hap)(hpp)⁺ (*m/z* 343, 5.5%). Appearance of peaks due to various species can be explained with the help of the following reactions.

Complex 1 and 2 exhibit peaks at *m/z* 180, 12.2% and 16.2% respectively, due to Co(sal)⁺. In the complex 3, a peak at *m/z* 194 (13.5%) appears due to Co(hap)⁺ and the peak at *m/z* 208 (10.8%) is due to Co(hpp)⁺. No peak corresponding to Co(hap)⁺ or Co(hpp)⁺ is observed in complex 1 and 2 respectively. These results indicate that salicylaldehyde is bound to the cobalt atom more strongly as compared to hydroxyaryl ketones. The complex [Co(sal)(hap)]⁺ exhibits peaks at *m/z* 301 (2.7%) and at *m/z* 329 (5.4%) due to Co(sal)₂⁺ and Co(hap)₂⁺ respectively. In the complex [Co(hap)(hpp)] peaks at *m/z* 329 (8.1%) and at *m/z* 359 (8.1%) are due to Co(hap)₂⁺ and Co(hpp)₂⁺ respectively. The spectra of all the complexes exhibit peaks due to Co₂L₂L'⁺ and Co₂LL'⁺ ions which might have been formed by the loss of either of the two ligand moieties from the dimeric species.

Fig. 1. Mass spectrum of [Co(hap)(hpp)].

In some cases the peaks due to such oligomeric species are quite abundant, for example, in the complex **3**, the peak at m/z 551 due to $[\text{Co}_2(\text{hap})(\text{hpp})_2]^+$ is the base peak (100%) and the relative abundance of the peak at m/z 537 due to $[\text{Co}_2(\text{hap})_2(\text{hpp})]^+$ is 86%. In some complexes the peaks due to other oligomeric species are most abundant, for example, in complex **1** and **2**, the peak at m/z 481 due to $\text{Co}_2(\text{sal})_3^+$ is the base peak (100%). Peaks due to other higher oligomeric species such as Co_2L_4 , Co_2L_5 , Co_3L_5 are also quite abundant (Table 2). Thus the formation of oligomeric species is very commonly observed in these complexes as reported earlier also in case of the mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals²⁵.

Experimental

1-Phenylbutane-1,3-dione (Sisco Chem) and 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione (Sisco Chem) were purified by recrystallization from hot ethanol. Salicylaldehyde (Merck), 2-hydroxyacetophenone (Boehringer, Germany), 2-hydroxypropiofenone (Fluka), pentane-2,4-dione (K. Light) and ethanol were purified by distillation $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Fluka) was used as supplied.

Cobalt was determined volumetrically by EDTA using xylenol orange as indicator²⁶. Specific conductances were measured at room temperature (~300 K) in DMF by a Systronics direct reading 304 conductivity meter using a glass cell having a cell constant of 1.0 cm^{-1} . IR spectra of the complexes (KBr) were recorded in the region $400\text{--}4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer. TGA and DTA studies were carried out on a Rigaku Thermoflex PTC-10A instrument under nitrogen atmosphere. Magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature (~300 K) on a Gouy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as a calibrant. Electronic spectra were recorded in DMF on a Hitachi U-200 spectrophotometer. The FAB mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 Mass spectrometer/Data system using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. Carbon and hydrogen analyses were carried out on a Heraeus Carlo Erba 1108 instrument.

Synthesis of mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} :

To an ethanolic solution of cobalt(II) nitrate (~3.72 mmol in ~10 ml ethanol) a mixture of the two different carbonyl compounds (~3.72 mmol each) in ethanol (10 ml) was added with continuous stirring at room temperature. A clear solution was obtained. The pH of the reaction mixture was raised to ~7.0 by adding 5% sodium hydroxide solution with constant stirring. The pH was measured with the help of a pH paper and stirring was continued for another 4–5 h. The solid complexes separated, were filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

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